

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B028
 Date: 12 Jul 2004
 Take Off: 13:22:35 18:10:31
 Landing: 16:15:25 20:51:20
 Flight Time: 2:52:50 2:40:49

Trials Instructions: ITOP – Transit to Horta via Porto, intercepting N. American pollution
Operating Area: Cranfield -Porto-Horta

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Reeves	Reading University
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
7	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
8	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
9	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
10	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
11	Mission Scientist 2/WAS	Ally Lewis	York University
12	Ground crew	Andrew Boardman	Avalon aero
13	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B028 Track 12-JUL-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B028

Date: 12th July 2004

Project: ITOP, transit Cranfield to Horta via Porto

Location: Cranfield- Porto-Horta

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg comments
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130150		INU to Nav.		
132235		T/O	0.0 kft	213 From Cranfield
133000		ASPS opened		
133000		HORACE crash		
134600		J/W zero cal.		
135008	140337	Run 1	10.0 kft	243
140400	141049	Profile 1	10.0 - 16.0 kft	247
scientific aims abandoned due to lack of time				
141056	142855	Run 2	16.0 kft	249
150600		HORACE crash		
154955	160226	Run 3	10.0 kft	185 descent during run to 5.0 kft
161525		Land	0.0 kft	346 At Porto
162300		GPs posn. on stand		41 14.40N 08 40.56w
162300		INU posn. on stand		41 13.48N 08 41.05W
Ground power not available at Porto, HORACE powered down				
170000		Power on		
170000		INU aligned		at GPS posn: 41 14.41N 08 40.56W
181031		T/O	0.0 kft	From Porto
183211		HORACE crash		
205120		Land	0.0 kft	092 At Horta
205541		Final GPS position		38 31.26N 28 42.98W

ITOP – Transit to Horta via Porto with possibility of intercepting US pollution

Mission Scientists: Claire Reeves

Date: 12/7/04

Outline schedule:

07:00 - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

09:00 - Air Crew Briefing

11.00 - Take-off

Location: Cranfield -Porto-Horta

Aim: To transit to Horta and to intercept pollution to the east of the Azores at around 20-25W and 3 km altitude.

Sortie Detail

- 7/03:22:2
1. T+0 Take Off. Head towards 50N 8W and perform a run of at least 20 mins at constant altitude (about FL100) in clear sky for calibration purposes. (40)
 2. T+40 Profile ascent at 1000ft/min to cruise altitude (FL250 to FL280). (20).
 3. T+60 Transit to Porto (OPO, 41°14'53"N, 008°40'53"W). Transit to include 20 mins at constant altitude between FL100 and FL150 for calibration purposes.
 4. Land at Porto.

Ground power is required at Porto to keep instruments running and warm.

- ST 8:0
13:50 Wk → 14:03:37
P1 14:04:00 →
- FL160!
14:10:56 →
- pdD 15:16:04 Z
5. T+0 Take Off. Head towards Horta (HOR, 38°31'12"N, 028°43'02"W) and perform a run of least 20 mins at constant altitude (about FL100) in clear sky for calibration purposes. (40)
 6. T+40 Profile ascent at 1000ft/min to cruise altitude (FL250 to FL280). (20).
 7. T+60 Transit towards Horta.
 8. Profile descent at 1000ft/min to reach FL080 at 38°30N, 20°W.
 9. Perform a straight and level run at around FL080 to 25°W on a westerly heading.
 10. Transit to Horta to include 20 mins at constant altitude around FL100 for calibration purposes.
 11. Land at Horta.

B028 Track 12-JUL-04

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

CAPT: ALAN FOSTER

Flight No B...028.....

Date 12/07/2004.....

Page 1... of 3.....

PAN, CRAWFIELD

Video Tapes
V8
No.
Ends
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	52 04.36	} GC ALIGN
Long	000 37.48	
Time	09 57 20	
Status	✓	✓

DRS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
HORACE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SATCOM	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
09:00:00	BOOTED OFF NORMAL				HARD DISC			
	NO CRASHES NOTICED							
11:18:00	HORACE SHUTDOWN							
11:20:00	BOOT OFF			DKA 100				
11:30:00	CABIN TEMP	27.1°C		38% RH	(AT CORE CONSOLE)			
12:35:00	CABIN TEMP	27.3°C		38% RH	(" " ")			
13:01:50	INU → NAV							
13:21:35	T/O							
13:30:00	ASPs OPEN							
13:30:00	HORACE CRASH							
13:46:00	TWC status light flashing							
13:46:00	T/W zero cal							
13:53:05	TWC turned off/on							
14:04:00	START PROBLEMS !							
14:21:27	TWC turned off							
14:28:55	end of run 2, start probe ascent but at > 1000 ft/min as need to get to Porto.							

Fri 17th

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B028 12/07/2004

Instruments

TWC FITTED, HEATERS COME ON ON GROUND IF ~~HEAT~~ HEATER SELECT SWITCHED FROM "OFF"

NEW SIG. REG. CABLE FITTED. ROSEMOUNT SIG. OK, NO HIEMANN BIT CHANGE WHEN CAL SELECTED

NO TIME DISPLAY RFC

RFC IMAGE "BURNT-OUT" IN BRIGHT CONDITIONS

AMTG NO DISPLAY

TWC FAILED IN FLIGHT

AMTG ALL LEDs CEASED FLASHING - TIME DATA APPEARS OK, HITTING THE PANEL ILLUMINATES THE LEDs

FFC }
DFC } FORGOTTEN ON FINAL DESCENT
JFC }

Aircraft